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Evaluation of the market potential of HiPIMS and advanced coating technologies

Final Report

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Executive Summary

The European Organization for Nuclear Research, known as CERN, is an international organization with a focus on fundamental physics research. It operates the worldwide largest particle accelerator complex and the world's most powerful particle collider, the Large Hadron Collider. Currently, a worldwide community of scientists and engineers develops a concept for an even large particle collider, the Future Circular Collider (FCC) with a circumference of almost 100 km. Within the scope of EASITrain¹, a H2020 project funded by the European Union that is coordinated by CERN, key technologies for the FCC are advanced. The Vienna University of Economics and Business contributes with studies that aim at studying how the society can best profit from the technologies that CERN develops together with industry for its particle accelerator developments. The focus of these efforts was on finding yet unidentified applications for technologies needed in the manufacturing process of high-field superconducting magnets and superconducting radiofrequency systems.

The teams worked to understand the challenges when aiming at transferring advanced coating technologies that are developed for superconducting radiofrequency cavities to a broad range of societal applications. Getting an in depth understanding of the limiting factors can also help identifying pathways to lower the cost of the technology, broaden the landscape of companies that can offer the technology and making the technology more accessible to a wide range of applications for the benefit of every single person. One coating technology was particularly put in the focus of the research: High Power Impulse Magnetron Sputtering (HiPIMS). CERN is interested in the growth potential of market applications that may be able adopt this elusive technology to increase the quality and value of a diverse set of products. Such, public investments in high-tech developments for fundamental physics research can be an effective lever to increase the competitiveness of European high-tech industries and to ensure that taxpayer's money is fed back to the society with additional benefits for everyone. The overarching goal of ultimately controlling the costs and increasing the performance for taking advantage of HiPIMS coatings for the Future Circular Collider is subdivided into sub-goals which are pursued simultaneously.

The research revealed that thin-film coating technology has already been widely implemented in several industries, such as the cutting tool manufacturing industry. HiPIMS remains, however, an elusive technology that is still characterized by high investments, a limited availability of experts who can make good use of this technology and for which a clear catalogue of market applications has not yet been established. Our research has also shown that HiPIMS is very well suited to add value in industries where high-quality standards are predominant and production costs play a minor role due to inelastic demand. The qualitative data collection highlighted four high potential application fields. These fields include the automotive, the medical, the communication and the glass production industry. These

industries offer adequate market sizes and exhibit sufficiently large growth potential to profit from the adoption advanced coating technologies and which are able to make use of superior quality of respective goods. Some of them are already in the process of adopting HiPIMS.

To sum up, the adoption of HiPIMS is connected with various uncertainties although recent developments have shown that there is the possibility, that HiPIMS will be adopted by selected industries on a larger scale. Especially the predicted ban of galvanization in the European Union could contribute to the desired widespread adoption of HiPIMS in the coating industry as an environmentally friendly technology and promote growth in the HiPIMS industry in Europe. A key challenge remains the availability of a sufficient amount of highly qualified experts with cross-cutting skills. Such people will be key to help spreading the adoption of advanced coating technologies and are required to transfer this high-tech process to the market. Consequently, continues advanced training in this domain, as showcased by the EASITrain Marie-Curie action will remain an important ingredient to create innovations in the European Union in a sustainable way.

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1 Introduction

Within the scope of EASITrain, a H2020 project funded by the EU, multiple projects have been conducted for the FCC project at Vienna University of Economics and Business. The focus of these previous efforts was on finding alternative applications for technologies needed in the manufacturing process of superconducting magnets and analyzing the most promising application fields. This project constitutes a follow-up project that aims to help CERN lower the costs for their planned Future Circular Collider, which is meant to take over from the LHC and extend its research. The following paragraphs define the scope, challenges and objectives of the project.

1.1 Problem Statement

CERN, the European Organization for Nuclear Research conducts research in the field of particles and their fundamental structures. Hereby, CERN itself is in charge of the design and the construction of extremely complex and scientific instruments, such as the particle accelerator and detectors. The largest particle accelerator, the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) will reach the end of its life by 2040. To ensure the scientific advancement, CERN initiated a feasibility study for a Future Circular Collider (FCC), together with 150 academic facilities (CERN, 2019).

For the construction of a particle accelerator of these dimensions and performance standards, CERN is in need of a substantial amount of Niobium, which is especially suited for this purpose due to its high level of conductivity for radiofrequency cavities to accelerate the particles. As Niobium is a very expensive material, it constitutes an relevant cost factor in the design and construction process. Due to that, CERN instigated research in the field of coating and alternatives to the usage of Niobium material, eventually leading to the conclusion that making use of the HiPIMS (High Power Impulse Magnetron Sputtering) coating technology substantially decreases costs since only little amounts of the material are required to produce superconducting cavities by coating inexpensive copper cavities.

As of today, HiPIMS is a technology, which is used in a certain niche area because hardly any coating producers offer this coating. This enables the few producers to charge a relatively high price for this service. The two prior research projects have already identified the main benefits of the HiPIMS technology, namely the ability to coat three-dimensional surfaces, long durability and the precision, with which coating can be applied. Based on these advantages, the prior groups have thus created a shortlist with potential use cases that currently still require further examination and verification (Fuchs, Grech, Wolf & Zsilavec, 2019).

However, some of the initially found application fields (i.e. the skiing and racing industry) were studied in a recently conducted proof of concept. After analyzing the results of wear and transparency tests for Titanium Dioxide (TiO₂) coatings, the findings presented on the one hand a higher resistance against scratches but on the other hand an increased visibility of scratches on the coated surface would be the

result. Consequently, it is important to keep looking for alternative applications for HiPIMS coating in order to ultimately increase the number of use cases for the technology, eventually leading to an increase in demand for HiPIMS coating and supply, and thus achieving a lower equilibrium price (Gutleber et al., 2020).

Another issue that arises with the usage of HiPIMS is the fact that it only represents a rarely used option in the majority of industries where PVD coatings are common. It is therefore vital to find ways to support further implementation of the HiPIMS coating technology in industries in which HiPIMS has already been applied before.

1.2 Objectives

The team aims to understand the past, current and futures challenges that coating machine producers have faced and will face in order to gain a deeper understanding of what would be required to encourage additional demand for HiPIMS-based coating, eventually believed to trigger further supply and lower pricing. CERN is interested in the growth potential of several coating industries, as their aim is not only to make use of high-quality instruments for their research activities, but also to incentivize stakeholders to adapt to new innovative procedures.

In order to achieve the overarching goal, it is important to understand the status quo of the HiPIMS technology with its key players, cost structure and current application fields. To evaluate future potential, it is of utmost importance to consider potential application fields as well, as these constitute potential for producers to adapt to advanced coating techniques like HiPIMS. Ultimately the group aims to achieve coming up with growth potential for certain industries, namely trends and drivers that trigger the adoption to high-level coating.

2 Methods

The objective of this chapter is to provide an overview of the methods used to elaborate the market potential of high value use cases of HiPIMS and other advanced coating techniques. The initial start is a technology description of HiPIMS, followed by techniques used in data collection, processing and analysis, which is based on two main pillars; conducting expert interviews and using the gained information to perform the technology competence leveraging method (TCL).

2.1 HiPIMS as an advanced coating technology

As a prerequisite for the desired elaboration of use cases and their market potential for HiPIMS mainly secondary research resources, such as research papers, journals and scientific publications, are utilized. A keyword-based literature research for both input materials into current coating processes, as well as coating techniques is used to provide for the macro perspective necessary to distill such fields. Afterwards, a comparison of HiPIMS to other coating procedures, with a later focus on high technology coating procedures, is conducted.

Primary research is used in the next step of the research approach. Conducting interviews with partners, experts and stakeholders is the core piece of this report. First, coating machine producers and their respective representatives by means of database-aided research, in addition to the identification of industry experts and academics with a background in HiPIMS or related fields and technologies were identified. Next, pyramiding is used to identify other stakeholders, such as research institutions, foil producers and experts from additional markets using HiPIMS or other advanced coating procedures.

The following 18 experts were interviewed:

Company Logo	Name of the Company	Name of the Expert
	CemeCon AG	Dr. Christoph Schiffers
	CemeCon AG	Dr. Ing. Beate Hüttermann
	Oerlikon Balzers Coating Germany GmbH	Dr. Frank Jungblut
	Oerlikon Balzers Coating Germany GmbH	Dr. Denis Kurapov
	Europäische Forschungsgesellschaft Dünne Schichten e.V.	Dr. Andreas Panckow

	TU Wien	Univ. Prof. Dipl. –Ing. Dr. mont. Paul Heinz Mayerhofer
	Filzwieser GmbH	Ing. Lukas Stockinger
	Fraunhofer Institut	Dr. -Ing. Ralf Bandorf
	4A Plasma	Dr. -Ing- Gerhard Eichenhofer
	SML	Dipl. -Ing. Robert Preuner
	University of Sheffield	Arutium P. Ethiasarian PhD
	Nano4energy	Dr. Ivan Fernandez Martinez
	Muenz-Pvd	Prof. Dr. Wolf-Dieter Münz
	IHI Hauzer Techno Coating BV	Michiel Eerden
	Hueck Folien GmbH	Dr. Stephan Trassl
	Tumbleweed	Michael Sandrieser
	Kunststoff-Institut Lüdenschied	Carl Schulz M.Sc.
	Oerlikon Balzers Coating Germany GmbH	Dr. Canet Acikgoz

Table 1: Interview Overview (Deutschbauer, 2021)

2.2 Current application fields

Current application fields are identified by evaluating the data gained from the interviews and research papers. By using data triangulation, the results, which are obtained from the interviews, are compared with the secondary research data, obtained from online sources, to increase the validity and reliability and to reduce the risk of false interpretations. This results in the following 5 confirmed current application fields:

- Residential Building Construction
- Industrial Machinery Manufacturing
- Computer and Peripheral Equipment Manufacturing

- Communications Equipment Manufacturing
- Motor Vehicle Parts Manufacturing

The North American Industry Classification System (NAICS), which categorizes industries by using a universal 4-digit code, is used to categorize the identified current application fields (and also the potential application fields in a following chapter). NAICS is a standard used by the Federal Statistical Agency to classify commercial entities. Its purpose is to collect, analyze and publish statistical information about the U.S. commercial economy (NAICS, 2020). The decision on which NAICS industries to use for the categorization of the current application fields was made by looking up use cases in the NAICS directory.

The current 5 identified application fields are further evaluated regarding current market size, key rationale for adoption and future growth potential/ trends and drivers. This is done by using research papers and other secondary data sources. The growth of the relevant market segment is evaluated by means of proxies, utilizing the growth rate of the market of the industry.

The estimated size of the industry is not equivalent to the size of HiPIMS and related technologies within that industry but have nonetheless been included for demonstration purposes.

2.3 Potential application fields

Making use of and relating to the findings of a previous student group, which used the technology competence leveraging method (TCL), including but not limited to the technological constraints and additional benefits emerged through the expert interviews, new potential application fields are identified. This approach is believed to be suitable for the initial establishment of a large list of applications which is expected to provide useful insights in assessing their suitability to partake in a HiPIMS technology transfer as well as their likelihood of adopting HiPIMS-based coating machinery production (by means of horizontal portfolio integration of existing coating machine producers or backwards integration of players within the coating-as-a-service / VAS market). The most promising potential application fields are selected by using a top-down approach, narrowing down fields based on evaluation of adoption by experts. This analysis yields a list of 12 vetted, potential application fields.

The assessment of the potential of application fields was done by using the insights gained from the 18 interviews with machine manufacturers, research institutes, coating experts, education institutes and manufacturers. The names of the experts are anonymized for the feasibility voting. High, medium and low potential is illustrated by means of a table with a color scheme code. The green fields indicate that the interviewed person sees a high potential, orange means the potential is given but with some bigger implications or it not mentioned, and red indicates the expert states that there is no potential in this industry. Industries with less than 5 votes for high potential are classified as low potential, between 5 and 8 votes as medium potential and with 9 or more votes for high potential as high potential fields. For

instance, the industry field Clay Product and Refractory Manufacturing shows 5 green, 12 orange and 1 red cell. This therefore indicates that the application has medium potential.

To assess which application fields, offer the highest potential, the number of times high potential has been mentioned by the experts, were summed up in the row “sums”. With these results, the likelihood of an adoption of a HiPIMS-based production and its potential is elaborated. 4 high potential fields, 5 medium potential fields and 2 low potential fields were identified.

Again, the market growth of the 4 high potential application fields is estimated by using the data available for the industry. As a last step, catalysts for development and limiting factors are investigated by, again, using data from the expert interviews and secondary research data.

2.4 Milestone Plan

In order to ensure an efficient and structured progress, several milestones are merged in a plan, which provides an overview of the most important steps in the advancement of the project. Elaborated details to certain methods can be found in the according chapters.

Figure 1 – Milestone plan (Schmidle, 2020)

3 HiPIMS as an advanced coating technology

In order to elaborate the potential of advanced coating technologies, an overview of currently used coating technologies within the PVD-based technologies subset, their potential for further adoption and growth in new fields, alongside the catalysts enabling wide-spread adoption, shall be approximated by using the HiPIMS technology as a proxy.

3.1 General overview of advanced coating technologies

Figure 2 – Classification of the coating procedures according to the initial state of the coating material (Hütteneider, 2020)

Coating procedures can be classified by the initial state of the coating material as gaseous, liquid, dissolved and solid. The gaseous coating procedures can subsequently be divided into chemical vapor deposition (CVD) and physical vapor deposition (PVD). PVD procedures are widely used across many industries. They are further split up into different specialized procedures. This chapter focuses on HiPIMS which itself is part of the sputter procedures. HiPIMS sets better quality standards through a higher ionization, which is responsible for the use benefits later discussed. This distinguishment is important because the individual material and substrate characteristics differ between different applications. Therefore, various coating procedures compete with one another, especially if they are

closer “related”. In many cases there is not only one possible way for coating a surface. In one case minimal costs are of highest priority and sometimes a smooth surface for example. Consequently, a best fit must be found (Schiffers, 2020).

3.2 Technical advantages of PVD-procedures and HiPIMS

PVD

Physical vapor deposition procedures in general are known for the variety of substrate materials that can be coated. They can be used for coating metals, alloys, ceramics, glass and plastics for example. Moreover, there is an almost unlimited choice of coating materials such as metals, alloys, semiconductors, metal oxides, carbides, nitrides, cermets, sulfides, selenides and tellurides for example. PVD procedures also allow producers to freely choose the substrate temperature. They achieve excellent coating adhesion and enable easy influenceability of the microstructure by the choice of process parameters. Those characteristics make PVD procedures suitable for many applications and are the reasons which make PVD a broadly and often used coating procedure in different industries (Eisenmenger-Sittner, 2020).

Some of the disadvantages of PVD procedures compared to other coating techniques are the limitation to coating materials able to enter the gaseous phase, comparatively low coating rates and layer thicknesses. Furthermore, the advantages mentioned above are only possible because the procedures are also comparatively very technically demanding processes (vacuum technology) and for some of them coating geometrically complex components is difficult (Eisenmenger-Sittner, 2020).

Arc

The arc process is one of the standard processes for the production of nitride hard coatings and can also be used advantageously for many other types of coatings. Numerous developments around the arc technology have been carried out at the IWS. The vacuum arc is a highly ionized gas discharge that burns in the steam it generates. Today, it represents the dominant source for industrial hard material coating. The discharge burns in the ionized vapor of the cathode material and is thus largely independent of ambient pressure. Vacuum arc discharges can therefore in principle be operated from ultra-high vacuum to the atmospheric pressure range, with the characteristics of the discharge at higher pressures approaching those of atmospheric arc discharges (Fraunhofer Institute, 2020).

HiPIMS

HiPIMS itself is a special PVD sputtering procedure which utilizes extremely high-power densities in short pulses (impulses) of tens of microseconds at low duty cycle (on/off time ratio). It distinguishes itself from other sputter procedures by its unique features such as high degree of ionization of the sputtered substrate and a high rate of molecular gas dissociation which result in high density of deposited films. The peak cathode power increases the extent of ionization and dissociation. The maximum is determined by the transition of the discharge from glow to arc phase. The peak power and the duty cycle are selected to maintain an average cathode power like conventional sputtering (Gudmundsson and Lundin, 2020).

The higher amount of ionization enables a denser layer structure which is also more uniformly built up than with conventional sputter procedures. With the layer thickness comes another big advantage of the HiPIMS technology. The layer thickness can vary from 1 μm up to 15 μm whereas conventional sputter procedures achieve a maximum layer thickness of 7 μm . The technology also enables a smoother surface without droplets as it can be seen in the figure below. This makes it perfectly suitable for applications with high surface quality requirements (Schiffers, 2020).

Figure 3 - Smooth, droplet-free coatings (CemeCon 2020)

Comparison between ARC – CVD – HiPIMS

	ARC	CVD	HiPIMS
SURFACE	Droplets	Rough	Smooth
COATING TEMPERATURE	500°C	1000°C	500°C
MAX. LAYER THICKNESS	4 µm	10 – 15 µm	12 µm
RESIDUAL STRESS OF THE COATING THICKNESS	High compressive stress	Tensile stress	Residual stress management for low compressive stress
DUCTILITY OF THE LAYER	High	Low	Very high
EASY PRODUCTION	Yes	No (precursor)	Yes
FLEXIBILITY	Low	None	High (all materials, all substrates)
MINI TOOLS	No	No	Yes

Table 3 – Comparison of different coating procedures (CemeCon, 2020)

This comparison efficiently illustrates the advantages of HiPIMS. The table above shows the comparison between three different gaseous coating procedures. Arc and HiPIMS are also closely related since both are PVD procedures. As it can be seen, one of the most significant advantages of the HiPIMS technology is the smooth surface, while the Arc technology leaves droplets and the CVD technology in general has a rougher surface which is due to the fact that there is a significantly higher ionization with HiPIMS. Therefore, the coatings are denser and more compact. Consequently, the coatings are more ductile while having the same hardness. This can normally only be achieved with alloys because higher hardness mostly involves higher brittleness (CemeCon, 2020).

However, this could not be confirmed by Oerlikon Balzers who tried to verify this hypothesis by conducting several tests which neither disproved nor proved this feature (Kurapov, 2020). Furthermore, sputter procedures need less heat than CVD procedures, so Arc and HiPIMS only need half of the heat that CVD requires. Another aspect that separates HiPIMS from Arc is the maximum layer thickness which is three times higher. Since HiPIMS is a sputter procedure, there is an unlimited material variety due to the sheer endless possibilities of combinations of the elements of the periodic table to produce coatings. Because HiPIMS does not create droplets it can also be used for very small and complex geometries (CemeCon, 2020).

The HiPIMS technology is limited mainly by its technically demanding level. There are more powerful generators needed to enable this high degree of ionization. This means there are significantly higher fixed costs than with other procedures. Since a vacuum is required, it is not possible to produce in an assembly line style. Therefore, high quantities are not feasible or simply not economical (Schiffers, 2020). Further limitations are mentioned in the conducted proof of concept.

Proof of concept

The proof of concept for scratch resistance of polymer foils enables a better understanding of the limitations of plastic foil coatings. Scratch and transparency tests for multiple coatings were conducted by H. Rojacz, M. Premauer and E. Badisch of AC2T research GmbH upon request by Dr. Gutleber in 2020. According to the findings of the wear tests, namely the scratch tests and Taber Abrasion tests, the mass loss and gravimetric wear correlates. It can be stated that 0.2 μm and 0.3 μm TiO₂ (Titanium Dioxide) coatings show a promising scratch resistance. However, uncoated samples show the least visibility of scratches compared to surfaces coated with TiO₂. This means that scratches on HiPIMS-coated surfaces appear less often but if they do, they are more visible. The main findings of the transparency tests state that the transparency decreases with increasing coatings thickness, which was found to be the case for all samples, thus ruling out HiPIMS-based coating with TiO₂ for use-cases necessitating optical consistency despite wear (Gutleber et al. 2020)

4 Current HiPIMS application fields

According to various experts and leaders in the field of HiPIMS coating processes, the HiPIMS coating technology is **already the common standard in today's cutting tools industry**. On top of that, the application of High-Power Impulse Magnetron Sputtering has turned out to be quite **useful for the coating of architectural glass** due to its thermal insulation properties and **for automotive engine components** as well (Schiffers, 2020). Furthermore, **HiPIMS has turned out to be of significant usage in the semiconductor industry, the automotive industry and has been used to coat the latest iPhone 12 Pro**.

4.1 Residential Building Construction - 2361

HiPIMS coatings are currently **employed in the coated glass market**, in which **architectural glass is the predominant sector**.

4.1.1 Architectural glass market size

According to market reports, the global market for residential building construction industry totaled \$4,171.3 billion in 2017 and is forecasted to hit \$6,800.9 billion by 2022, constantly growing at a compound annual growth rate (=CAGR) of **10.3% for the period of 2017-2022**. Of course, this number does not equal the market potential of HiPIMS coatings in these markets, it rather **gives an approximate outline of the growth potential within the markets**. If the interviewed experts are to be believed, HiPIMS has the potential to rise at an even higher growth rate which renders its increased application in this area very promising (BCC Research, 2020).

Figure 4 – Global Residential Building Construction market (Tanson, 2021)

4.1.2 Key rationale for adoption

The core benefits that the HiPIMS coating technology provides the coated glass industry, especially architectural glass, are one the hand enhanced adhesion and on the other increased protection against UV-radiation in order to support thermal insulation. In other words, windows, which are made of coated glass, allow utmost transmission of visible light, while at the same time reflecting the sun’s infrared energy. Consequently, the air conditioning and heating costs of a building can be reduced (Grandview Research, 2020).

A very interesting market for this application field is China, where buildings are directed by law to uphold a certain level of thermal insulation due to environmental restrictions (Schiffers, 2020).

4.1.3 Future growth potential/Trends and drivers

Regarding foreseeable trends and drivers in the Residential Building Construction industry, the expected residential boom in the United States will most likely stimulate demand for coated glass within the next years. Furthermore, rising environmental awareness in terms of global warming, energy efficiency and rise of green buildings is a development that can potentially boost the need for coated glass substantially (Grandview Research, 2020).

4.2 Industrial Machinery Manufacturing - 3332

The cutting tool industry was amongst the first implementers of HiPIMS coating and can be considered as the only application field where objects are coated using the HiPIMS technology on a regular basis.

4.2.1 Industrial machinery manufacturing market size

As of today, the global cutting tools market size is estimated to be \$34.42 billion, possibly growing at a compound annual **growth rate of 3.25%** during the forecast period 2019-2025. “Such affluence of cutting tools can be attributed to heavy industrial operations and unprecedented production demand surfacing by the means of global industrialization and the necessity for an operative and well-functioning economy.” (Industry ARC, 2019)

Nonetheless, it is important to add that this number does not accurately reflect the market potential of HiPIMS, which is expected to be significantly less. Instead, one gets a decent indication regarding the eventual growth performance of HiPIMS in this specific market.

Figure 5 – Global Cutting tools market (Tanson, 2021)

4.2.2 Key rationale for adoption

Since cutting tools have to endure a lot of friction and mechanical stress, they are coated using HiPIMS due to its enhanced wear resistance and durability properties in order to increase the tools' overall endurance. Moreover, HiPIMS coatings prevent premature cutting-edge chipping and reduce eventual edge build-up (Schiffers, 2020).

Especially in Central European markets like Germany and Italy the competitive landscape concerning HiPIMS coatings in the cutting industry is intense. Instead of just offering lower prices to beat the competition, the market participants mainly aim to differentiate themselves from their competitors by offering the best service and coating quality (Jungblut, 2020).

4.2.3 Future growth potential/trends and drivers

Due to an economic slowdown in 2019 which had a strong impact on the automotive industry, one of the most significant application areas for cutting tools, and the Covid-19 outbreak in 2020, the manufacturing industry as a whole has been hit hard. As a result, manufacturing companies were forced to temporarily shut down their plants leading to a lower demand for cutting tools as of today. Nonetheless, as the severity of the crisis wears off, plants are expected to reopen and therefore the demand for cutting tools will reinvigorate. Moreover, the continuous growth of the aerospace industry, oil and gas, shipbuilding and other heavy engineering sectors is driving the demand for cutting tools. Taking all these factors into account, the demand for HiPIMS coatings is presumed to grow within the following years (Mordor Intelligence, 2019).

4.3 Computer and Peripheral Equipment Manufacturing – 3341

Semiconductors have been considered a suitable use case at a very early stage despite the fast-changing nature of the industry.

4.3.1 Computer equipment manufacturing market size

“The global computer hardware market is expected to grow from \$862.93 billion in 2020 to \$944.09 billion in 2021 at a **CAGR of 9.4%**. The growth is mainly due to the companies rearranging their operations and recovering from the COVID-19 impact, which had earlier led to restrictive containment measures involving social distancing, remote working, and the closure of commercial activities that resulted in operational challenges. The market is expected to reach \$1178.15 billion in **2025 at a CAGR of 6%.**” (The Business Research Company, 2020)

Realistically, objects coated HiPIMS will only attain an exiguous share of the estimated market potential. Nevertheless, the global computer hardware market is yet another great potential use case that is forecasted to steadily grow.

Figure 6 – Global computer hardware market (Tanson, 2021)

4.3.2 Key rationale for adoption

As it allows for increased ductility compared to other advanced coating technologies, some companies have taken advantage of HiPIMS for chip manufacturing. In addition, HiPIMS coatings provide the substrates with mechanical properties such as hardness, adhesion, mechanical, and fracture strength. Oerlikon Balzer’s involvement in the HiPIMS coating technology originated from producing machines for chip manufacture (i.e. metallization of their structure). However, Oerlikon sold the semiconductor/metallization division a few years ago but believes that Evatec, the company that bought it, is still offering HiPIMS solutions today (Kurapov, 2020).

4.3.3 Future growth potential/trends and drivers

The global computer hardware market is already quite high and is projected to continue to grow as seen on figure 6. Higher ionization is possible when coating with HiPIMS compared to MS sputtering which is certainly a driver in this industry (Eichenhofer, 2020). The fast-changing character of the semiconductor industry and the need to optimize such products can be seen as a driver for the HiPIMS technology since it provides better and smoother coating results than other coating techniques which is key especially for coating small parts.

4.4 Communications Equipment Manufacturing – 3342

The latest iPhone released by Apple in October 2020, the iPhone 12 Pro (in gold), is one of the most recent new use cases where the HiPIMS coating technology has been applied to the frame of the phone. If the interviewed experts are to be believed, this specific use case within smart phone manufacturing will be the first of many.

4.4.1 Communications equipment manufacturing market size

“The Global Communications Equipment market accounted for \$601.69 billion in 2019 and is expected to reach \$2,231.18 billion by 2027 growing at a **CAGR of 17.8%** during the forecast period. Increased growth of cellular stations and the need for next-generation-ready network equipment for 5G networks are driving market growth. However, high costs of new product development are restraining market growth.” (Research and Markets, 2020)

Certainly, the estimated market potential for communications equipment is not attainable for HiPIMS-related products. In fact, only an immensely small portion of this market is currently covered by HiPIMS. However, the forecasted growth in this sector indicates that the potential for HiPIMS in this market is high, considering various expert opinions that believe that HiPIMS is about to increasingly enter this specific market.

Figure 7 – Global communications equipment market (Tanson, 2021)

4.4.2 Key rationale for adoption

As opposed to all the structural stainless-steel bands of other color variations of the iPhone 12, which have been coated using the conventional PVD method, the structural band of the iPhone 12 in gold has been coated with HiPIMS in order to take advantage of the coating procedure’s excellent wear resistance (Apple, 2020).

4.4.3 Future growth potential/trends and drivers

As shown above, the global communication equipment market is set to grow significantly over the next years. Cellphone-manufacturing companies may look to find new innovative ways to differentiate their products from the competitors' while also enhancing the overall quality of their products. This is exactly where HiPIMS coatings could come into play, as their properties provide the applicators with great benefits in terms of product quality and marketability.

If certain experts are to be believed, further smartphone giants such as Samsung and Huawei have already initiated and intensified their R&D activities regarding potential HiPIMS coatings (Fernandez, 2020).

4.5 Motor Vehicle Parts Manufacturing – 3363

Another current use case of HiPIMS coatings are engine components such as fuel injectors in automobiles.

4.5.1 Motor vehicle parts manufacturing market size

“The market for auto parts manufacturing was estimated at roughly \$363 billion in 2018 and is anticipated to reach a value of around \$532 billion by the end of 2029, influenced by the cyclic trend of the automotive industry and new product launches. The auto parts manufacturing market is expected to grow at a moderate **CAGR of ~3%** during the assessment period.” (Persistence Market Research, 2019) Considering HiPIMS is still a very special coating procedure that is applied in specific use cases, the aforementioned market potential is not achievable by HiPIMS coatings. A continuous growth in the market however supports the argument of a rising potential of HiPIMS in the respective market.

Figure 8 – Global motor vehicle parts manufacturing market (Tanson, 2021)

4.5.2 Key rationale for adoption

As these automotive components are usually exposed to high contact pressure, HiPIMS and its durable coatings have proven to be useful in this industry as well. Further advantages that this sputtering procedure provides automotive parts with are enhanced aesthetics appearance, increased corrosion resistance, scratch resistant and higher surface hardness. Unlike the cutting tools industry however, HiPIMS is applied rather rarely in this area, which can be mostly attributed to the higher costs incurred during a HiPIMS coating process compared to other advanced coating techniques and the continuous phase out of the diesel engine (Schiffers & Kurapov & Fernandez, 2020).

4.5.3 Future growth potential/trends and drivers

In terms of ongoing trends and drivers that can and will influence this industry, two major developments have been identified. The slowdown in the manufacturing sector, which has been caused particularly by the Covid-19 pandemic, is forecasted to have a negative impact on the growth of the global automotive industry in short to medium term. This will most likely severely influence the utilization of HiPIMS coatings within industry as automotive companies might look to save costs.

Additionally, the current trend towards E-mobility and away from diesel-engined vehicles, where HiPIMS-coated injectors are common, will most likely decrease the potential usage of HiPIMS in the future (Schiffers & Kurapov, 2020).

5 Potential application fields

As of today, HiPIMS is only used in a very limited field of applications. The expansion potential of HiPIMS-based coating remains broad, as there are diverse potential application fields which do not use HiPIMS yet or only use it to a limited extent. The most promising potential application fields are ranked as low, medium and high potential and are listed in the following subchapters.

Application field	3391 - Medical Equipment & Supplies Manufacturing	3363 - Motor Vehicle Parts Manufacturing	3272 - Glass & Glass Product Manufacturing	3342 - Communications Equipment Manufacturing	3333 - Commercial & Service Industry Machinery Manufacturing	3272 - Electric Lighting Equipment Manufacturing	3271 - Clay Product & Refractory Manufacturing	3399 - Other Miscellaneous Manufacturing	3364 - Aerospace Product & Parts Manufacturing	3261 - Plastics Product Manufacturing	3341 - Computer & Peripheral Equipment Manufacturing	8114 - Personal & Household Goods Repair and Maintenance
Machine manufacturer 1												
Machine manufacturer 2												
Machine manufacturer 3												
Machine manufacturer 4												
Research institute 1												
Research institute 2												
Coating expert 1												
Coating expert 2												
Coating expert 3												
Education institute 1												
Education institute 2												
Manufacturer 1												
Manufacturer 2												
Manufacturer 3												
Research Institut 3												
Startup 1												
Machine manufacturer 5												
Machine manufacturer 6												
Sum	15	11	10	10	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	2

Figure 9 – Potential Application Fields of HiPIMS (Deutschbauer, 2020)

5.1 Use case evaluation

There are 5 low potential, 5 medium potential and 3 high potential application fields identified which are further described and evaluated in the following subchapters.

3341 - Computer & Peripheral Equipment Manufacturing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computer Chips 	3342 - Communications Equipment Manufacturing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cellular Telephones • Protective Screen Covers 	3272 - Electric Lighting Equipment Manufacturing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lightning Equipment • Batteries 	3272 - Motor Vehicle Parts Manufacturing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engines • Gears
3364 - Aerospace Product & Parts Manufacturing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satellites • Drones • Spacecrafts 	3399 - Other Miscellaneous Manufacturing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Watches • Jewelry • Ski 	3391 - Medical Equipment & Supplies Manufacturing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stents & Catheters • Prostheses & Implants • Crowns & Bridges 	8114 - Personal & Household Goods Repair and Maintenance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relics • Coins
3261 - Plastics Product Manufacturing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food Packaging 	3272 - Glass & Glass Product Manufacturing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Airplane Windows • Solar Panels 	3333 - Commercial & Service Industry Machinery Manufacturing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microscopes • Lenses • Optical Classes 	3271 - Clay Product & Refractory Manufacturing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Armatures • Tableware

Table 2: Identification of high-potential application fields (Deutschbauer, 2021)

5.1.1 High potential fields

Application fields with a majority of 9 or more expert votes for high potential are classified as high potential application fields.

Medical Equipment and Supplies Manufacturing - 3391

There are several potential use cases in the field of medical equipment and supplies manufacturing, which include but are not limited to prostheses, implants, catheters, dentures, crowns and bridges. Stents manufactured with an ion-protected process using HiPIMS would have the advantage that they are composed of a well-adhering and closed layer (Pankow, 2020). The enhanced durability can also be of benefit (Jungblut & Kurapov, 2020).

Dentistry applications, such as crowns and bridges are also feasible according to Oerlikon Balzers, which also have their own business units for medical services (Acikgoz, 2021).

Regarding the development of the market size, medical implants market accounted for \$85,389 million in 2019, and is estimated to reach \$147,464 million by 2027, therefore registering a CAGR of 7.2% from 2020 to 2027 (Allied Market Research, 2020).

This segment scored the highest number of 15 experts agreeing on its high potential. Only 3 out of 18 experts rate medical equipment with a medium level of potential.

Motor Vehicle Parts Manufacturing - 3363

According to Dr. Schiffers from CemeCon, the trend towards e-mobility and the associated special parts in general is certainly favorable for the HiPIMS market and represents a source for innovation.

Engines, injectors, gears and other parts of motor vehicles can be coated with HiPIMS and have a high potential according to the majority of experts. This is especially due to the fact that these components have to endure significant amounts of friction which can be endured by applying tribological HiPIMS coatings. In addition, various automotive parts made up of aluminum are likely to be adequate use cases as well (Münz, 2020).

It is important to point out that the application of HiPIMS coatings is not just limited to engine parts. In fact, some car manufacturing companies have taken advantage of this sputtering technique in terms of decorative coatings of external car parts (Fernandez, 2020).

Motor vehicle parts manufacturing is a high-potential industry given that 11 experts estimated the value as high.

Glass and Glass Product Manufacturing - 3272

Glass and glass product manufacturing is one out of 4 high-potential fields which were analyzed.

10 out of 18 experts believe that this application field has high potential.

Especially solar panels and airplane windows seem promising. A further potential use case is flexible optical glass for displays, an area that has experienced significant growth recently, where coatings with HiPIMS are a great fit due to their aforementioned, beneficial properties (Mayerhofer & Panckow, 2020). Additionally, companies such as Euroglas coat their glass bottles using the magnetron-sputtering technique in order to ensure heat insulation and increased protection against UV-radiation (Panckow & Euroglas, 2020).

Regarding the market size of the global flat glass market, it was valued at \$115.8 billion in 2019 and is expected to witness a considerable revenue based CAGR of 7.3% from 2020 to 2027. “Recovery of the construction sector in developed economies such as North America and the rapid expansion of new construction spending in emerging economies of Asia Pacific is predicted to be the key driver of the market for flat glass.” (Grandview Research, 2020)

Communications Equipment Manufacturing - 3342

Manufacturing cellular telephones is already a current application form as mentioned in chapter 4.4. There is potential to expand the application in this field according to Christoph Schiffers and Andreas Panckow. Paul Heinz Mayerhofer points out that HiPIMS is already used in the coating for the iPhone 12 and other phone production firms might follow.

Correspondingly, other smartphone manufacturing giants such as Samsung and Huawei have started to consider HiPIMS as a viable coating option for their products (Fernandez, 2020).

Communication equipment manufacturing scores 10 out of 18 votes for a high-potential field. None of the experts thinks there is low potential and 8 indicate medium potential.

5.1.2 Key adoption criteria

The 4 identified high-potential fields, as well as current application fields for HiPIMS and related advanced coating technologies, showcase certain characteristics, rendering them suitable for new technology adoption in the first place.

High-value-added industries

For some industries, coating objects using the HiPIMS method is not feasible. Especially low-value-added industries cannot be considered potential application areas as the perceived benefits, that a HiPIMS coating adds, do not outweigh the rise in costs that are incurred throughout the coating process (Panckow & Bandorf, 2020).

Conversely, high-value-added industries aiming for superior quality instead of price differentiation are believed to be the most suitable industries for HiPIMS coatings. Since production costs typically do not play a crucial role for companies from these industries - whereas the product quality certainly does – high-value-added industries are the most promising when it comes to the adoption of the HiPIMS technology (Mayerhofer & Ethiasarian, 2020).

High end-product differentiation

In end-product markets, showing little differentiation amongst suppliers of goods, efforts to adopt new technologies enabling differentiation are near zero.

However, in end-product markets featuring suppliers competing on product differentiation, the initial hurdles of adopting HiPIMS (and related advanced coating technologies), primarily consisting of capital expenditures and staff education, would be perceived as a post-adoption benefit, creating further barriers-to-entry alongside product distinguishment.

“If you have a conventional product that does not have any special requirements, there will not be a switch to the HiPIMS technology.” (Bandorf, 2020)

Inelastic demand or price agnosticism

For industries, solely focusing on product quality, that would effectively be closely tied to the adoption of a bleeding-edge technology, costs are considered irrelevant. Relevant examples would most certainly be found within life-sciences & medicine.

These characteristics primarily cater towards the justification of currently presenting hurdles across all relevant dimensions for adoption: capital, labor, and time.

5.2 Catalysts for development

Given increases in widespread adoption, integration of knowledge in academic curricula, the dynamics surrounding adoption limitations and enabling forces would be subject to change and could potentially lower barriers for advanced coating technology adoption.

As of this writing and since the introduction of HiPIMS, combined research efforts have led to the development a wide array of technological solutions, particularly within the Physical Vapor Deposition technologies subset of coating procedures, often accompanied by the displacement of technologies positioned within the Chemical Vapor Deposition by the now newly established PVD-procedures, for reasons of cost, technological fit and regulation around environmental and health concerns pertaining to CVD-based procedures.

Potential catalysts enabling these aforementioned changes in market dynamics are primarily believed to be found in regulatory changes, pertaining to health and environmental protection efforts, by experts consulted.

5.2.1 Replacement of galvanization coatings with PVD-coating procedures

Potential EU-wide ban of respective substrate materials

EFDS Expert Panckow expects bans on Chrome 6, amongst other substrates, due to environmental concerns, which could potentially not only create a new market for HiPIMS-based coating, but further additionally shift demand from traditional “In-solvent” Coating procedures to other, related advanced coating technologies.

“HiPIMS is very well suited to replace galvanization.” (Panckow, 2020)

In anticipation to a potential ban, several companies including Kolzer SRL, a coating machine manufacturer, have started adding galvanization alternatives to their product portfolio, such as UV PVD Chrome, an ecologically sound chrome plating, which replaces the electroplating treatments.

Some of the properties include hardness, resistance, time optimization, and reduction of processing costs. The UV and PVD combination is safe, economical and more environmentally friendly than galvanic, proceeding to be eliminated.

5.3 Limiting factors

HiPIMS adoption in the coating industry is determined by several limit factors, that need to be overcome in order to achieve wide-spread market adoption.

5.3.1 Switching costs

In terms of implementation costs that a company incurs when setting up its machinery for HiPIMS coatings, a precise estimation of the total amount of costs is certainly hard to form. Firstly, the implementation costs largely depend on the size of the company that needs HiPIMS coating machines or, to be more exact, on the number of machines that are to be acquired by the company. Since the HiPIMS coating machines have a market price varying between 1.1 to 2 Million Euros, this initial decision on how many machines should be installed is already of great importance. Secondly, in order to guarantee that the coating machines run smoothly, continuous in-depth training of staff poses another considerable cost factor. Nonetheless, the modalities by which a company trains its personnel also varies strongly from enterprise to enterprise, which renders it difficult to quantify the amount of costs necessary.

However, it is important to mention that if a company decides to adapt a pre-existing coating procedure provided by the manufacturer of the coating machine, training expenditure of staff can be cut significantly due to the fact that one only needs to follow predefined steps to complete a HiPIMS coating process. Relating to this, Michiel Eerden of Hauzer stated that “in this case, you can basically pick a person up from the streets to take care of the HiPIMS coating process” (Eerden, 2021).

Nonetheless, skilled personnel remain crucial to ensure a smooth coating process and to intervene in case of technical malfunctions of the machines.

5.3.2 Sharing economy

The consumer electronics market witnessed a significant growth in retail volume, owing to an increase in the preference for premium products. However, the emerging consumer patterns of renting, optimizing and sharing, coupled with high appliance penetration rates among households, are expected to impact the demand for new appliances, and thus, limiting the usage of PVD coatings.

5.3.3 Self-induced lack of obsolescence

In some instances, manufacturers of certain (consumer) goods simply do not want their products to have an enhanced product-life cycle in order to ultimately achieve and maintain a higher purchase frequency (Eichenhofer, 2020).

Costly HiPIMS coatings, which would ensure increased durability, therefore will not be applied in these cases as the rise in costs is not economically and technically reasonable.

5.3.4 Covid-19 impact

The temporary closing of manufacturing companies, especially in the automotive industry, also lead to a decreased demand in the coating industry. Generally, the Covid-19 crisis has affected industries worldwide and will force some companies to tighten their budgets considerably. Especially restricting R&D expenditure, which is crucial for a potential adoption and further development of the HiPIMS coating technology within firms, will severely impact the future adoption rate of cost-intensive advanced coating technologies such as HiPIMS.

5.3.5 Lack of scalability

Since HiPIMS-based coatings are strongly relying on several procedural steps such as for instance vacuuming or preparing the surface, serial production is rendered rather difficult to execute. Being able to coat objects in serial production allows for higher throughput rates and thus would make HiPIMS coating more qualified for mass market adoption. According to multiple experts however, HiPIMS is not destined for mass market adoption. Instead, the sputtering procedure has already found the majority of its most suitable niches in certain industries (cutting tools, semi-conductors) and will continue to operate in niche markets. As a result, Research & Development efforts for serialization which would support the scalability of HiPIMS have remained low (Schiffers & Eichenhofer, 2020).

5.3.6 Low competitive forces

Currently, only a limited number of companies which offer HiPIMS solutions exist in the European market. The overall level of competition within the HiPIMS market is therefore relatively weak and further Research & Development expenditure in order to outcompete rivals with innovative approaches is disincentivized. Furthermore, high entry barriers in the form of patents, established sales/distribution channels and huge capital requirements mitigate the threat of new entrants which consequently hints that the competitive landscape will not change drastically in the near future.

5.3.7 Low demand and supply

In order to increase the adoption of the HiPIMS coating technology in existing and new markets, demand and supply need to be promoted. This would not only support the sputtering procedure's path to a more widespread utilization but also help lowering the current high costs that HiPIMS coatings cause for both coating firms and their clients. As there are only a few companies offering HiPIMS solutions with no signs of significant new entrants and as the market for HiPIMS is considered a niche market, an increase in supply and demand is not necessarily foreseeable.

6. Conclusion

To sum up, HiPIMS is a technology that can add various benefits in high-value industries, where quality standards are high due to its main advantages in terms of higher durability and immaculate surface characteristics. Nevertheless, the wide-spread adoption in the coating industry has not taken place so far due to the lack of scalability and high acquisition costs of HiPIMS coating machines. For existing producers, the additional costs clearly outweigh the perceived increase in quality, which prevents existing coating producers from adopting to advanced coating technologies such as HiPIMS.

The profound analysis of the industry has shown that previous assumptions only have conditional accuracy as HiPIMS is already applied in various industries, such as the cutting tool industry. Qualitative data gathering brought about salutary insights into the world of HiPIMS and the rationale behind adoption. Regarding future developments HiPIMS is most likely to be applied and adopted in industries where the desire for extraordinary quality regardless of any additional costs is predominant, such as the medical supply industry with the production of stents and implants in the dental-health segment.

However, it is key to understand the criteria for adoption and the threat of substitution when the attempt of projection to other industries is realized. Especially the lack of scalability and the planned obsolescence of certain products do not lead to demand for sophisticated coating. In mass-markets it is also the case that conventional coating procedures already brings the desired benefits with regards to the cost-limitations, which damps the demand for even better coating procedures such as HiPIMS.

Our concluding recommendation is to focus on high-value industries and the markets stated with the biggest growth potential, such as the medical supply, glass, communication equipment and automotive industry. To fulfill the objective of incentivizing industries to adopt to technological advanced technologies it is key to reach out to main players stated in our analysis namely Hauzer, Oerlikon Balzers and Cemecon as these represent the protagonists in the European Market with appropriate market power. These companies could help to fulfill the objective to accelerate HiPIMS in the geographic area of the European Union and finally lead towards greater supply and demand for HiPIMS machines and the coated products.

7. References

Allied Market Research (2020). Medical Implant Market By Product Type (Orthopedic Implants, Cardiovascular Implants, Spinal Implant, Neurostimulators, Ophthalmic Implants, Dental Implants, Facial Implants, and Breast Implants) and Biomaterial Type (Metallic Biomaterials, Ceramic Biomaterials, Polymers Biomaterials, and Natural Biomaterials): Global Opportunity Analysis and Industry Forecast, 2020–2027. Retrieved from: <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/medical-implants-market> (accessed on 14.01.2021)

Apple (2020). Apple Event — October 13. Youtube. Retrieved from: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KR0g-1hnQPA&t=2827> (accessed on 21.11.2020)

BCC Research (2020). Residential Building Construction Industry: Global Markets to 2022. Retrieved from: <https://www.bccresearch.com/market-research/manufacturing/residential-building-construction-industry-global-markets.html> (accessed on 14.01.2021)

CemeCon (2020). HiPIMS. The Future of PVD Coating Technology. Retrieved from: <https://hipims.cemecon.de/en/> (accessed on 20.11.2020)

Cern (2019). About Cern. Retrieved from <https://home.cern/about> (accessed on 15.10.2020)

Eisenmenger-Sittner, C. (2017). Physik und Technologie Dünner Schichten. Retrieved from https://static.ifp.tuwien.ac.at/homepages/Personen/duenne_schichten/pdf/t_p_ds_kapitel2.pdf (accessed on 27.12.2020)

Euroglas (2020). SILVERSTAR- Glasbeschichtung, Produktion Wärme- und Sonnenschutzglas. Retrieved from: <https://www.euroglas.com/unternehmen/faszination-glas/glaserstellung/herstellung-beschichtetes-glas.html> (accessed on 05.01.2021)

Executive Office of the President (2017). North American Industry Classification System. Retrieved from: https://www.census.gov/eos/www/naics/2017NAICS/2017_NAICS_Manual.pdf (accessed on 19.11.2020)

Fraunhofer Institute (2020). High-power impulse magnetron sputtering. HIPIMS. Retrieved from: <https://www.ist.fraunhofer.de/en/technologies/physical-vapour-deposition/hipims.html> (accessed on 22.11.2020)

Fraunhofer Institute (2020). Arc-Verfahren (Vakuumbogenbeschichtung). Retrieved from: https://www.iws.fraunhofer.de/de/geschaeftsfelder/pvd_nanotechnik/pvd-schichten/technologien/arc-verfahren.html (accessed on 27.12.2020)

Fuchs, S. / Grech, F. / Wolf, E., / Zsilavec, T. (2020). Report On HiPIMS: Assessing The Potential Using The TCL Method. Vienna University of Economics.

Grandview Research (2020). Coated Glass Market Size, Share & Trends Analysis Report By Application. Retrieved from: <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/coated-glass-market> (accessed on 07.01.2021)

Grandview Research (2020). Flat Glass Market Size, Share & Trends Analysis Report By Application (Architectural, Automotive & Transportation), By Product (Tempered, Laminated, Insulated, Basic), By Region, And Segment Forecasts, 2020 – 2027. Retrieved from: <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/global-flat-glass-market> (accessed on 14.01.2021)

Industry ARC (2019). Cutting Tools Market – Forecast (2021 - 2026). Retrieved from: <https://www.industryarc.com/Report/16304/cutting-tools-market.html#:~:text=The%20global%20cutting%20tools%20market,the%20forecast%20period%202019%2D2025> (accessed on 14.01.2021)

Mordor Intelligence (2019). Global Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD). Coatings Market. 2020 – 2025. Report. Hyderabad. India.

Persistence Market Research (2019). Enhanced Vehicle Performance Will Remain the Focal Point of Auto Parts Manufacturing Market Players. Retrieved from: <https://www.persistencemarketresearch.com/mediarelease/auto-parts-manufacturing-market.asp> (accessed on 14.01.2021)

Research and Markets (2020). Communications Equipment - Global Market Outlook (2019-2027). Retrieved from: https://www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/5116446/communications-equipment-global-market-outlook?utm_source=CI&utm_medium=PressRelease&utm_code=jjplk6&utm_campaign=1442385++Worldwide+Communications+Equipment+Industry+to+2027+-+by+Type%2c+Component%2c+Application%2c+End-user+and+Geography&utm_exec=jamu273prd (accessed on 14.01.2021)

Rojacz, H. / Premauer, M. / Badisch, E. (2020). Scratch resistance of polymer foils. Report. AC2T research GmbH. Wiener Neustadt.

The Business Research Company (2020). Computer Hardware Global Market Report 2021: COVID-19 Impact And Recovery To 2030. Retrieved from:
<https://www.thebusinessresearchcompany.com/report/computer-hardware-global-market-report-2020-30-covid-19-impact-and-recovery> (accessed on 14.01.2021)

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10. Appendix

10.1 Medium potential application fields

Medium potential application fields are use cases with between 5 and 8 expert votes for high potential.

Clay Product and Refractory Manufacturing - 3271

Armatures and tableware are optical applications in the segment of clay product and refractory manufacturing which have a medium to high potential for the use of HiPIMS.

5 out of 18 experts rate the potential as high.

Beate Hüttermann from CemeCon sees a high potential for this segment especially with products such as doorknobs and armatures which are intensively used and therefore need good protective adhesion. The company Hauzer is specialized in producing machines which are suitable for such applications.

Commercial and Service Industry Machinery Manufacturing - 3333

Microscopes, lenses and optical glasses are an application field with medium potential according to the interviewed field experts. Coating with HiPIMS changes the length of the light which gets through optical glasses and may have an impact on the vision, which needs to be taken into strong consideration (Hüttermann, 2020).

5 out of 18 experts see high potential and 13 mediocre potential.

Electric Lighting Equipment Manufacturing - 3351

Andreas Panckow mentions that manufacturing lighting equipment, especially in terms of encapsulations for OLEDs, can be optimized by using HiPIMS. Furthermore, batteries can be made more durable with HiPIMS as well.

13 out of 18 experts see only medium potential and the remaining 5 state high potential. Therefore, the overall potential is rated as rather low.

Aerospace Product and Parts Manufacturing - 3364

Satellites, drones and spacecrafts could potentially be coated with HiPIMS as this industry is not considerably cost sensitive as Arutium P. Ethiasarian explains. However, Ralf Bandorf and other experts have the opposite opinion that other coating techniques are more suitable for this industry.

5 out of 18 experts see a high potential and the majority of 12 experts rate the potential as medium as it is hard to investigate on what techniques and materials are used in the aerospace industry. 1 expert even sees no potential at all.

Other Miscellaneous Manufacturing – 3399

Other miscellaneous manufacturing includes watches, jewelry and sports equipment such as skis.

These potential applications are estimated to be medium-potential application fields by 12 out of 18 experts. 1 expert sees no potential in this application and 5 rate the potential as high.

10.2 Low potential application fields

Application fields with less than 5 expert votes for high potential and a majority of votes for no potential/not mentioned and no potential are classified as low potential application fields.

Plastics product manufacturing - 3261

From a technical standpoint, High-Power Impulse Magnetron Sputtering is applicable on plastic foils, which includes the use of barrier layers, antireflection layers or foils with specific wavelengths to see the inside of the packaging while keeping the heat radiation outside at the same time. As they are usually larger than for instance cutting tools though, power transmission could be a potential pitfall. Additionally, HiPIMS requires a lot of electrical power so coating larger surfaces equals higher variable costs per coating process which renders the coating process rather uneconomical. Moreover, even premium plastic foils outgas when heated up which subsequently deteriorates the vacuum during the HiPIMS process and ultimately leads to an inferior coating quality (Panckow, 2020).

Moreover, Mr. Panckow states that achieving the prior mentioned layer benefits is possible with normal sputtering and in addition offers an opportunity for production with HiPIMS. The cost factor in this industry, however, plays a big role as well and HiPIMS is too expensive as of now to coat plastic packaging (Panckow, 2020). Furthermore, various thin foil producers incorporate the desired properties directly into the foils which makes additional coating layers obsolete (Stockinger, 2020).

While the quality of thin foil surfaces after a HiPIMS coating procedure is superior or at least as good as the quality of a surface coated with a different advanced coating technology, the coating rate tends to be significantly better for other coating options. In addition, these other advanced coating technologies such as DC (Reverse) Pulse are generally cheaper (Eichenhofer, 2020).

In most cases, producing significantly enhanced thin foils by coating them with HiPIMS is simply not necessary since the products are often not supposed to have an increased endurance for example. Planned obsolescence is believed to be a significant factor which undoubtedly limits or even denies the usage of HiPIMS in the thin foil industry (Eichenhofer, 2020).

“Visions of HiPIMS use cases in the plastics industry have not been confirmed” states Gerhard Eichenhofer from 4APlasma due to the fact that plastic foils seemed promising at first but are not suitable for the mass market because of the price factor.

Only 4 out of 18 of the interviewed experts rate the potential in the field of plastic product manufacturing as high, 11 think it is feasible but not worth the additional costs and 3 see no potential at all.

Computer and Peripheral Equipment Manufacturing - 3341

Dr. Frank Jungblut and Denis Kurapov mention that use cases in the semiconductor industry, especially the potential for computer chips, are given (Jungblut & Kurapov, 2020). Frank Jungblut also states that HiPIMS meets the special requirements for the semiconductor industry, which is not suitable for all coating techniques.

Only 4 out of 18 experts share this opinion and identify this industry as a high-potential one, 1 expert states computer and peripheral equipment manufacturing has no potential and the rest indicate a medium level of potential.

Personal and Household Goods Repair and Maintenance - 8114

Relics are a use case due to their 3D-structure which can be seamlessly coated with HiPIMS (Hüttermann, 2020). Coating coins with HiPIMS is feasible but might be cost intensive (Panckow, 2020).

The majority of 16 out of 18 experts do not see high potential in the segment of personal and household goods repair and maintenance. 1 expert sees no potential at all.

10.3 List of conducted expert interviews

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
1	Cern	Dr. Johannes Gutleber	Project Partner	19.10.2020	German

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
2	CemeCon AG	Dr. Christoph Schiffers	Sales Coating-Technology	13.11.2020	German

Key insights: The main market for HiPIMS is currently in China and other parts of Asia. CemeCon sold an average of 1 HiPIMS coated machine per year for 10 years. Today, they sell an average of 1 machine per year that is not HiPIMS coated.

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
3	CemeCon AG	Dr. Ing. Beate Hüttermann	Executive Sales Director	16.11.2020	German

Key insights: Added value for HiPIMS must be created so that it is economically interesting to coat with it. The coating of skis is not a suitable field of application due to the size and thus the cost factor.

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
4	Oerlikon Balzers	Dr. Frank Jungblut	Global Account Manager	23.11.2020	German

Key insights: With HiPIMS, very good coating properties such as defect-free surfaces are achievable. Jungblut sees especially high potential in the semi-conductor industry.

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
5	Oerlikon Balzers	Dr. Denis Kurapov	Market Segment Manger Cutting Tools	23.11.2020	German

Key insights: Kurapov recommends value added pricing and sees high potential in the medical field. Oerlikon is selling items coated with HiPIMS either per piece or per machine run (multiple items are collected and then combined).

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
6	EFDS	Dr. Andreas Panckow	Network Manager	24.11.2020	German

Key insights: There is no need for single-use products to switch to HiPIMS. HiPIMS is very well suited to replace galvanization. Panckow expects bans on Chrome 6, among others, due to environmental concerns, which could create a market for HiPIMS.

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
7	TU Wien	Univ. Prof. Dipl. – Ing. Dr. mont. Paul Heinz Mayerhofer	Head/Member of Materials Science Research Division	01.12.2020	German

Key insights: HiPIMS is used in applications where price is not an important factor and the best quality is desired. Technology has little potential for changes pricewise according to Mayerhofer.

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
8	Filzwieser GmbH	Ing. Lukas Stockinger	Management/Member Research field	02.12.2020	German

Key insights: Filzwieser has no need for plastic film coating. The requirements for films, such as UV protection or heat protection, can be achieved almost equally well and more cost-effectively without coating.

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
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9	Fraunhofer Institute	Dr. -Ing. Ralf Bandorf	Head of Group “Highly Ionized Plasmas and PECVD”	02.12.2020	German
Key insights: HiPIMS is already well established in various markets. Bandorf states that HiPIMS offers coating with higher ionization and thus layers can be applied more densely.					

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
10	4A Plasma	Dr. -Ing- Gerhard Eichenhofer	PVD Expert	09.12.2020	German
Key insights: Less expensive and better technologies for coating thin foils exists.					

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
11	SML	Dipl. -Ing. Robert Preuner	Head of Research & Development	09.12.2020	German
Key insights: SML does not use HiPIMS or other advanced coating techniques. They have no need for it because direct integration of benefits into the material is possible. Mr. Preuner sees no potential for HiPIMS in the plastic foil market.					

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
12	University of Sheffield	Arutiu P. Ethiasarian PhD	Head of the National HIPIMS Technology Centre	11.12.2020	English
Key insights: It takes longer for HiPIMS to coat 1000 tools - but this is not that much if you divide it by 1000 tools. High value-added industries are most promising for an application with HiPIMS.					

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
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13	Nano 4energy	Dr. Ivan Fernandez Martinez	General Manager	14.12.2020	English
Key insights: The hardware power supply for HiPIMS is very expensive. The price difference between HiPIMS and MS sputtering is low if the coating is very thin.					

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
14	Muenz Pvd	Prof. Dr. Wolf- Dieter Münz	PVD Expert	30.12.2020	German
Key insights: HiPIMS has big potential for use cases which are coated with very thin and dense coatings. HiPIMS cannot completely replace MS sputtering.					

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
15	IHI Hauzer Techno Coating B.V.	Michiel Eerden	Director of Sales	21.01.2021	English
Hauzer focuses on the cutting tool industry and sees potential for HiPIMS in application fields which need the best technology.					

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
16	Hueck Folien GmbH	Dr. Stephan Trassl	Project Manager Research	17.01.2021	German
HiPIMS will become interesting when comparable process speeds are achieved and improvement in adhesion, layer quality, generation of completely dense layers, new optical properties, etc.					

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
17	Tumbleweed	Michael	Director of Sales	20.01.2021	German

		Sandrieser			
There is great potential for market growth in high value application fields such as the medical field and the aerospace industry.					

Interview No.	Company	Name of the interviewee	Position of the interviewee	Date	Language
18	Oerlikon Balzers	Dr.Canet Acikgoz	Market Segment Manager Medical Precision Components	26.01.2021	English
HiPIMS is already used in the dental industry since about one year.					

10.4 Company profiles

As of today, there are three notable machine manufacturers in Central Europe producing machines that are capable of High-Power Impulse Magnetron Sputtering coatings. The first one, CemeCon, is located in Würselen, Germany and has been offering HiPIMS solutions for coatings for over 10 years. The second machine manufacturer is Oerlikon Balzers and has its headquarters in Liechtenstein. The third producer, Hauzer, is a Dutch company owned by IHI Group from Japan.

CemeCon

German enterprise CemeCon represents one of the companies that have capitalized the most from the surge of HiPIMS in certain use cases. While they sold just one HiPIMS coating machine per year a decade ago, CemeCon sells only one machine that is not destined for HiPIMS coating on average nowadays. Overall, out of the 200 machines capable of coating with HiPIMS which are being sold per year in total, around 30 of them (15%) have been produced by CemeCon. As of today, their prices range from 1.1 to 1.6 Million Euros per machine, depending on the necessity of extra equipment (cooling system, surface conditioning) for the coating process.

Additionally, CemeCon does not only sell the coating machines, they also offer a contract coating service for their customers through which the customers can have their items coated by CemeCon at their facility. In fact, half of the enterprise's revenue is obtained through the sale of coating machines and the other half is realized through their contract coating service (Schiffers, 2020).

The company's key customer segment is the cutting tool industry, where sputtering has proven to be a suitable coating technique before. Furthermore, CemeCon exclusively sells its products to other commercial partners and businesses (B2B) in order to avoid interference with their clients' end

customers. Regarding the market regions served by CemeCon, the machine manufacturer has customers all over Europe, in South Africa, in South America and Asia. China, in addition to Europe represent the largest end customer markets as of today (Hüttermann, 2020).

Oerlikon Balzers

Oerlikon Balzers also provides coating solutions almost exclusively for the cutting tool industry but have recently expanded their operations to new industries such as the medical sector. Moreover, another commonality they share with CemeCon is the possibility for customers to either buy coating machines from the company or pay for its contract coating service. In contrast to CemeCon however, Oerlikon Balzers strongly focuses on contract coating as their main source of revenue and have subsequently become the world's top supplier of contract coating services by a large margin. Generally, the enterprise, which has its headquarters in Liechtenstein, manufactures coating machines primarily for its own usage rather than producing to sell them (Kurapov, 2020).

Oerlikon Balzers has sold around 1,100 coating machines to companies which were mainly form the cutting tools or the automotive sector. Depending on if the buying firms have their own R&D Department or if they just focus on the preexisting coating process, it is estimated that 20 – 30 employees of the buying firms are overseeing one coating machine (Jungblut, 2021).

In addition, High-Power Impulse Magnetron Sputtering is a fairly new coating option at Oerlikon Balzers since they have added the technology to their portfolio of coatings as recently. as seven years ago, considering that the first HiPIMS units were already being offered in the market 14 years ago. Another considerable disparity between the two machine producers is the fact that only about 10% of all contractual coating orders are completed using the HiPIMS method. While CemeCon has specialized in offering almost exclusively HiPIMS coating solutions, Oerlikon looks at each order individually and then decides together with the customer which of the coating procedures is the most suitable for their objects (Jungblut, 2020).

As Oerlikon is a very internationalized company operating in 100 locations in 37 countries worldwide, legitimate estimates concerning the cost structure of HiPIMS coating machines or its contract coating service are hard to make. Furthermore, it is notable that Oerlikon Balzers is not necessarily striving for price differentiation/reduction in order to fend off competition. Instead, the company focuses on value-added pricing; creating additional benefits for its customers is one of the company's core value propositions (Kurapov & Jungblut, 2020).

Regarding the number of staff, Oerlikon has around 11,000 employees out of which 7,800 are working in the field of Oerlikon Surface Solutions (OSS). Roughly 3,900 people are employed by Oerlikon Balzers and work in their Surface Solutions Department.

Hauzer

Hauzer is a Dutch coating specialist that has been pioneering in the fields of (plasma) coating for almost 40 years. Amongst their extensive portfolio of coating options, HiPIMS has proven to be a reliable procedure in the field of cutting tools. In fact, coating cutting tool components is Hauzer's most prominent application field of the HiPIMS technology. Amongst their customers, large entities such as Paul Horn and Walter AG are two prime examples that have openly communicated that are working with Hauzer's machines (Eerden, 2021).

However, Hauzer generally sees tribological coatings, which are universally of great use in areas where a substantial amount of friction needs to be endured, as a considerable application area. Therefore, the automotive sector in terms of engine parts such as injectors and the aerospace industry can rely on the advantageous properties that HiPIMS solutions provides its applicants with.

Regarding Hauzer's perception of HiPIMS as a viable coating technology in reference to more conventional coating procedures, the Dutch company views the sputtering technique to be destined for niche applications where high performance is crucial and thus the cost factor is not as decisive (Eerden, 2021).

Within the company, Hauzer has established two departments that focus on HiPIMS coatings: Process Engineering and Electrical Engineering. In total, around 10 employees oversee these two departments (Eerden, 2021).

Cost structure

Figure 10 – Production costs for HiPIMS coating (Hütteneider, 2020)

The costs for HiPIMS coating depend on a few factors, first one being the coating machine itself. It matters how expensive the machine was and how much coating room there is. Secondly, the costs differ from various coating materials and layer thicknesses. As confirmed by the interviews with CemeCon and Oerlikon Balzers, the production costs can be separated into two big parts. Depreciation and personnel being the bigger cost driver make up around 90%. On the other hand, consumption such as electricity, gas, and material make up around 10% of the total costs. One does pay per pass rather than per part. Therefore, it is highly important to design ideal brackets to use as much space as possible (Schiffers, 2020). To illustrate this, a quote from an interview with CemeCon is provided:

“The machine has a coating room of Ø400 mm x 400 mm. An order for 1800 drills with Ø6 mm x 60 mm can be processed in one pass. The duration of this process is about 4,5 hours long. For that CemeCon would charge around 1.500 EUR. Consequently, depreciation and personnel make up 1.350 EUR and electricity, gas, etc. 150 EUR” (Schiffers, 2020).

Regarding the pricing of Oerlikon Balzers it strongly depends on the country where the coating process takes place (Kurapov, 2020).